

Multimetal multiligand complex formation equilibria of copper(II), nickel(II) and zinc(II) with iminodiacetic acid and L-pyrrolidine-2-carboxylic acid in aqueous solution

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Abstract : Solution equilibria of homo and heterobinuclear complexes of Cu^{II}, Ni^{II} and Zn^{II} with iminodiacetic acid (IMDA = A²⁻) and L-pyrrolidine-2-carboxylic acid (proline = B⁻) as ligands have been investigated by pH-measurements in an aqueous medium and relevant stability constants have been evaluated using computer technique. The stability constants of binary, ternary and quaternary complexes are determined at 35 ± 1°C and at I = 0.1 mol dm⁻³ (NaNO₃). Complexes of the type [M₂(A)₂(B)]⁻ and [M¹M²(A)₂(B)]⁻ have been detected along with the various binary and ternary species. The observed order of the stability constants and probable solution structure of homobinuclear complexes have been discussed.

Keywords : Multimetal multiligand complexes, quaternary metal complexes, IMDA, proline.

Investigations of complexes consisting of two metal ions and two different ligands other than solvent may be utilized as a model for understanding the role of metal ions in various complex biological activities occurring in nature¹. Such complexes have important biological implications as they facilitate various enzymatic processes². Multimetal multiligand complexes are of great relevance also in the study of biofluids hyperaccumulated with metal ions³. Formation, structure and stability of binary and ternary metal complexes have been studied extensively in comparison to quaternary metal complexes⁴. However, multimetal multiligand complexes of transition metals with IMDA and proline ligands have not been attempted so far.

Thus, the present communication describes the equilibrium study on multimetal multiligand complex formation of M²⁺ ion (M²⁺ = Cu, Ni, Zn) with IMDA (A²⁻) and proline (B⁻) in an aqueous medium at 35 ± 1 °C and I = 0.1 mol dm⁻³ (NaNO₃).

Results and discussion

The overall stability constant for complex formation between metal ions M¹ and M² and two ligands A and B is expressed by :

$$\beta_{pqrst} = \frac{[M_p^1 M_q^2 A_r B_s (OH)_t]}{[M^1]^p [M^2]^q [A]^r [B]^s [OH]^t} \quad (1)$$

where p, q, r, s and t are stoichiometric numbers; p, q, r and s are usually positive number or zero. t is a negative integer for protonic species, positive for hydroxo species and zero for a neutral species.

IMDA (A²⁻) behaves as a tridentate ligand, the coordination taking place from the nitrogen atom and two carboxylato groups⁵. Proline (B⁻) usually functions as a bidentate ligand, coordinating through COO⁻ and N atom. Protonation constants for these ligands have been determined by Irving-Rossotti titration technique and are pre-

Table 1. Proton-ligand and hydrolytic constants in aqueous solution
Temp. = 35 ± 1 °C, I = 0.1 mol dm⁻³ (NaNO₃)

(a) Proton-ligand constants (log β_{00rst}) :

	p	q	r	s	t	log β _{00rst}
H ₃ A	0	0	1	0	-3	14.26
H ₂ A	0	0	1	0	-2	12.03
HA	0	0	1	0	-1	08.80
H ₂ B	0	0	0	1	-2	12.79
HB	0	0	0	1	-1	09.37

(b) Hydrolytic constants of M²⁺ (aq.) ions (log β_{p0rot}) :

	Ni			Cu		Zn		
M(OH)	1	0	0	0	1	-11.00	-7.60	-9.60
M(OH) ₂	1	0	0	0	2	-16.87	-13.10	-14.92
M(A)(OH)	1	0	1	0	1	-	04.29	-

sented in Table 1a. Whereas, values of metal hydrolytic constants (Table 1b) were taken as such from the literature⁶.

(a) *Metal-ligand formation constants of binary and ternary systems* :

Only MA, MA₂ and MB types of binary species have been detected in addition to protonated ligand species in the binary systems. Moreover, (CuA-OH)⁻ species is also identifiable at pH > 4 in CuA system.

log β values obtained for binary systems are reported in Table 2a.

Distribution data reveals [M(A)(B)]⁻ to be a remarkable species in (1 : 1 : 1) M²⁺ : A²⁺ : B⁻ system in the pH range ~2.5-7.5.

Speciation of M²⁺, HA⁻, HB and [M₂(A)₂(B)]⁻ in (2 : 2 : 1) M²⁺ : A²⁻ : B⁻ system in the pH range ~2.5-7.0 suggest the formation of homobinuclear [M₂(A)₂(B)]⁻ complex according to following equilibrium :

log β values of CuA and CuB suggest CuA to be more stable. Thus it appears that each of the IMDA ligand binds separately to Cu^{II} in a tridentate manner, in Cu₂(A)₂(B) system⁷. The two metals being bridged through carboxylato oxygen and imino nitrogen of proline, thereby giving a coordination no. of 4 to both the Cu^{II} atoms in homobinuclear ternary complex [Cu₂(A)₂(B)]⁻. This structural description for [Cu₂(A)₂(B)]⁻ species seems to be reasonable because the sum of twice the stability constant value for tridentate binding of IMDA with Cu^{II} and sta-

bility constant for bidentate binding of proline with Cu^{II} comes to be around 30.00 log units which is comparable with log β_{M₂(A)₂(B)} value of 27.00 obtained in Cu₂(A)₂(B) system. Similar arguments may also be applied for Ni₂(A)₂(B) and Zn₂(A)₂(B) systems.

(b) *Metal-ligand formation constants of quaternary systems* :

Complex of the type [M¹M²(A)(B)]⁺ is found to be the major species in (M¹)²⁺ : (M²)²⁺ : A²⁻ : B⁻ (1 : 1 : 1 : 1) system in the pH range ~2.5-5.5 according to following equilibrium :

Decline in the concentration of [(M¹)(M²)(A)(B)]⁺ species at pH > 5.5 gives indication of the dissociation of [(M¹)(M²)(A)(B)]⁺ species as per following equilibrium :

where, M¹ = Cu and M² = Zn, Ni; eq. (4) do not contribute to Ni-Zn system.

Concentration profile of Cu²⁺ : Ni²⁺ : 2A²⁻ : B⁻ (1 : 1 : 2 : 1) indicate heterobinuclear complex formation in the pH region ~2.5-6.0 according to following equilibria :

Table 2. Metal-ligand binary, ternary and quaternary constants in aqueous solutions^a

Temp. = 35 ± 1 °C, I = 0.1 mol dm⁻³ (NaNO₃) (standard deviations are ~0.1-0.5 in log units)

(a) Metal-ligand constants (log β_{p0rst}) : binary systems

	p	q	r	s	t	Ni	Cu	Zn
M(A)	1	0	1	0	0	8.95	10.35	6.16
M(A) ₂	1	0	2	0	0	14.50	19.00	10.29
M(B)	1	0	0	1	0	7.63	10.07	6.50

(b) Metal-ligand constants (log β_{p0rst}) : ternary systems

						Ni	Cu	Zn
M(A)(B)	1	0	1	1	0	19.09	21.72	18.19
M ₂ (A) ₂ B	2	0	1	1	0	24.73	27.00	22.60

(c) Metal-ligand constants (log β_{pqrst}) : quaternary systems

						Cu-Ni	Cu-Zn	Ni-Zn
M ¹ M ² (A)(B)	1	1	1	1	0	26.00	25.45	23.32
M ¹ M ² (A) ₂ (B)	1	1	2	1	0	34.00	33.80	31.00

^aCharges are omitted for clarity reasons.

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Equilibria (5) and (6) are also reported in systems, Cu-Zn, and Ni-Zn.

Step fall in $\text{Cu}^1\text{M}^2(\text{A})(\text{B})$ (1 : 1 : 2 : 1) complex after a wide maxima in the pH range ~3.5–8.5 was also reported.

Observed order of stability with respect to metal ion in mononuclear $\text{M}(\text{A})$, $(\text{MB})^+$ and $(\text{MAB})^-$ complexes (Table 2), fall in the Irving-Williams order⁸, $\text{Ni} < \text{Cu} > \text{Zn}$. Overall stability constants of binuclear β_{20210} and β_{11210} are found to be in the general order $\text{Cu-Cu} > \text{Cu-Ni} > \text{Cu-Zn} > \text{Ni-Ni} > \text{Ni-Zn} > \text{Zn-Zn}$; which forms composite Irving-Williams order.

Experimental

Ligands and metal salts were used as supplied and their solutions were prepared using double distilled water. Metal ion solutions were standardised by complexometric EDTA titration⁹. Carbonate free solution of NaOH, nitric acid (A.R.) and other chemicals used were of reagent grade. pH measurements were made on digital pH-meter (century model-CP 901-S) with a glass electrode (reproducibility ± 0.01 pH) at 35 ± 1 °C.

For the system under study following compositions were prepared.

- (i) 0.1 M (NaNO₃) + 0.002 M (HNO₃)
- (ii) (i) + 0.001 M (A/B)
- (iii) (i) + 0.001 M (A/B) + 0.001 M (M¹/M²)
- (iv) (i) + 0.002 M (A) + 0.001 M (M¹/M²)
- (v) (i) + 0.001 M (A) + 0.001 M (B) + 0.001 M (M)
- (vi) (i) + 0.002 M (A) + 0.001 M (B) + 0.002 M (M)
- (vii) (i) + 0.001 M (A) + 0.001 M (B) + 0.001 M (M¹) + 0.001 M (M²)
- (viii) (i) + 0.002 M (A) + 0.001 M (B) + 0.001 M (M¹) + 0.001 M (M²)

where (M), (M¹), (M²) are Cu, Ni, Zn as the case may be. Total volume in each case was raised upto 50 ml and ionic strength (*I*) of all solutions was maintained constant $I = 0.1 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ (NaNO₃). Each set of solution was then titrated against 0.1 M alkali (NaOH). The other ex-

perimental details have been described elsewhere¹⁰.

The β_{pqrst} values were evaluated using SCOGS computer program¹¹. Refined values of the constants were supplied to the computer as input data to obtain distribution curves of the complexes occurring at different pH. These distribution curves were further utilized to derive complex formation equilibria. Ionic product of water (*K_w*) and activity coefficient of hydrogen ion, under the experimental conditions was obtained from literature¹². The overall stability constant values are reported in Tables 1 and 2.

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